

Reactions of Nitrite with Nitric and Perchloric Acids

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The action of perchloric acid in displacing nitrous acid from a nitrite is similar to that reported earlier¹ for HCl and H₂SO₄. The simple displacement is followed by auto-oxidation. On the other hand, nitric acid may lead to a good deal of atmospheric oxidation. Theoretically, a small quantity of the nitric acid should completely convert all the nitrite to nitrate according to the mechanism suggested, but the minimum nitric acid requirement, actually observed, is 0.206 mole/mole nitrite.

In describing the reaction of sodium nitrite with HCl and H₂SO₄ in a previous communication¹, the present authors referred to reactions leading to auto-oxidation and aerial oxidation, respectively, of nitrous acid and formation nitric acid.

Reaction (i) will be unaffected whether it is carried out in presence or absence of air and will depress the acid requirement (of one mole of NaNO₂ for complete decomposition of the nitrite) to 2/3 mole of mineral acid since 1/3 mole of HNO₃ will be produced during the reaction.

Reaction (ii) will depress the value to 1/2 mole acid or less, but can take place only when air is present.

Since HNO₃ is one of the products formed, reactions (i) and (ii) should be inhibited if HNO₃ is used for titration, more so if HNO₃ is taken in a cell and nitrite added from a burette. Perchloric acid is a strong acid as well as a powerful oxidising agent and since oxidation is involved here, a titration with this acid is of interest. Hence in the potentiometric titrations described here, the behaviour of these two acids has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

All experimental arrangements were the same as described previously¹. In view of the importance of the inert atmosphere in the titrations involving nitrous acid, some of the titrations were also performed in an atmosphere of CO₂. Both direct and reverse titrations were performed. The results are summarised in the following tables. The nature of some titration graphs may be seen in Fig. 1 and 2.

1. Gyani and Prasad, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 155.

TABLE I

*Titration with nitric acid (direct).*V ml of x (M) NaNO₂ in cell and y (M) HNO₃ in burette.

V.	x.	y.	Inflection at moles HNO ₃ /mole NaNO ₂ .		Curve No.
A. In presence of air.					
20 ml	0.10	1.64	0.82	0.672	I
20	0.20	3.28	0.75	0.615	II
20	0.50	3.28	2.00	0.656	III
10	0.75	5.48	0.65	0.400	IV
10	1.00	3.28	1.00	0.328	
10	0.00	5.48	0.75	0.206	
B. In presence of CO ₂ .					
20	0.10	1.64	0.80	0.656	
20	0.20	3.28	0.80	0.656	
20	0.50	3.28	1.95	0.639	
10	1.00	3.28	1.95	0.639	

TABLE II

*Reverse titrations.*V ml of x (M) HNO₃ in cell and y (M) NaNO₂ in burette.

V.	x.	y.	Inflection at moles HNO ₃ /mole NaNO ₂ .	
A. In presence of air.				
20 ml	0.05	1.0	1.25	0.80
10	0.10	1.0	1.30	0.77
10	0.20	2.0	1.20	0.83
10	0.50	2.0	3.10	0.83
B. In presence of CO ₂ .				
20	0.05	1.0	1.30	0.77
10	0.10	1.0	1.30	0.77
10	0.20	2.0	1.30	0.77
10	0.50	2.0	3.00	0.83

TABLE III

*Titration with perchloric acid.*V ml of x (M) NaNO₂ in cell and y (M) HClO₄ in burette.

V.	x.	y.	Inflection at moles HClO ₄ /mole NaNO ₂ .		Curve No.
A. In presence of air.					
20 ml	0.1	1.56	0.85	0.663	I
10	0.2	1.56	0.85	0.663	II
10	0.5	2.65	1.20	0.612	III
10	1.0	2.65	2.10	0.550	IV
B. In presence of CO ₂ .					
20	0.1	1.56	0.80	0.624	
10	0.2	1.56	0.85	0.663	
10	0.5	2.65	1.25	0.662	
10	1.0	2.65	2.15	0.569	

TABLE IV

*Reverse titrations.*V ml of x (M) HClO₄ in cell and y (M) NaNO₂ in burette.

V.	x.	y.	Inflection at moles HClO ₄ /mole NaNO ₂ .	
A. In presence of air.				
10 ml	0.05	0.5	1.30	0.77
10	0.10	1.0	1.30	0.77
10	0.20	2.0	1.25	0.80
B. In presence of CO ₂ .				
10	0.05	0.5	1.20	0.83
10	0.10	1.0	1.25	0.80
10	0.20	2.0	1.20	0.83

DISCUSSION

We find a striking similarity in many of the results contained in Tables I and III. These are experiments in which we start with the sodium nitrite in the cell and add nitric or perchloric acid from a burette. If the initial concentration of nitrite is about 0.1M, one mole of the salt requires only 2/3 moles of the acid (HNO₃ or HClO₄) for complete displacement of nitrous acid. When air is excluded from the system, this ratio persists for increased initial concentrations of nitrite, but when air is present, the ratio shows a sharp fall as nitrite concentration is increased. Indeed, when NaNO₂ is 2M, the ratio falls to 0.21 (Table I).

It may be noted that in these titrations, the mixture in the cell remains nearly neutral till the inflection is observed. The solution then becomes acidic. Average concentration of nitrite during the experiment remains large. Seemingly, the simplest explanation for this ratio can be effected on the basis of auto-oxidation of the nitrous acid displaced in the first instance (reaction i).

The experiments, the results of which are contained in Tables II and IV, are similar to the extent that the mixture remains strongly acidic during much of the titration and the concentration of nitrite ions remains negligible till the titration is over. The acid requirement in these experiments remains close to 0.80 mole. Generally speaking, auto-oxidation is partially suppressed in acidic solutions. The reaction under these conditions conforms more nearly to simple displacement.

Two exceptions are noted to the above generalisation. Firstly, when the initial nitrite concentration is large and air is present (Table I), the ratio of acid may fall from 0.66 to 0.21. These results are simply explained if the existence of reaction (ii) is assumed. In this reaction, a particle is first formed in solution, which can combine with atmospheric oxygen. The net result is that some nitrite ions are converted into nitrate ions so that a correspondingly lower quantity of the mineral acid is required for decomposition of the rest of the nitrite. This oxidation is completely eliminated when CO₂ is bubbled (Table I).

The second exception is noted in Table III. Since CO₂ is being bubbled, the perchloric acid requirement should remain constant at 0.66 mole, but it falls to 0.57 when the initial concentration of nitrite is increased to 1M. Perhaps under these conditions, a little nitrite

is oxidised to nitrate, the oxygen coming from the perchloric acid. We were unable to demonstrate unequivocally, however, the reduction of perchloric to chloric acid by qualitative tests.

Nitric acid (ml) →
FIG. 1 (vide Table I).

Perchloric acid (ml) →
FIG. 2 (vide Table III).

It may be further noted that reaction (ii) is a triggered one. A little nitric acid added to the nitrite would displace a little nitrous acid, which is oxidised and regenerates the original nitric acid. The reaction will then go on in cycles till all the nitrite is consumed. A low ratio, such as 0.21 noted above, is therefore not surprising.

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